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Digital divide and digitalization in Europe: A bibliometric analysis

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Abstract

Research background: Digitalization and the associated digital divide are crucial issues impacting socio-economic development globally. Extensive research has examined digitalization and the digital divide in EU countries, but there is a lack of understanding regarding comparisons with studies conducted in Western Balkan countries. This study investigates digitalization trends in research from the past five years in both regions, focusing on efforts and factors contributing to the digital gap.

Purpose of the article: The study analyzes research on digitalization from 2018 to 2023 in the EU and Western Balkans. It explores factors causing the digital divide and efforts in digitalization, aiming to guide future research and policy for digital inclusion and sustainable development.

Methods: The study employs a meticulous data selection process, choosing Scopus as the database for its extensive coverage of diverse journals. A total of 1119 articles from EU countries and 277 from Western Balkan countries are selected for bibliometric analysis, adhering to PRISMA guidelines.

Findings & value added: The research reveals a growing interest in digitalization-related issues, demonstrating the multidisciplinary nature of ongoing research. It points out the distribution of publications on digitalization in the EU and Western Balkans countries. The EU focuses on digital technologies, economic growth, and sustainability, while Western Balkan countries focus on COVID-19 impact and digitalization in education and business. The research compares digitalization efforts in the EU and Western Balkan countries presented in the literature, pointing to new dimensions of the digital divide studies. It discusses how socio-economic contexts affect digital transformation and stresses the need for tailored policy approaches for digital inclusivity. These insights are of great importance for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners working towards global digital development and bridging the digital divide. The study lays the groundwork for future research and policy considerations, considering limitations like potential bias in databases and search criteria.

Introduction

Digitalization has been widely identified as the most significant technological megatrend (Reis *et al.*, 2020; Gajdzik *et al.*, 2021; Sun *et al.*, 2022a). It involves the continuous integration of digital technologies and digitized data throughout the economy and society, accelerating the pace of change affecting all aspects of our socio-economic life. According to Valenduc and Vendramin (2017), the term “digitalization” is not the irruption of a new revolution, but the pervasive synergy of digital innovations in the whole economy and society. It enables us to create and harvest value in new ways (Gobble, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2023; Plekhanov *et al.*, 2023).

Digital transformation is one of the European Union’s priorities, providing opportunities to strengthen Europe’s capacity for new digital technologies, creating new opportunities for businesses and citizens, and support-

ing the EU's green transformation to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 (Yin *et al.*, 2023). To guide the EU's digital transformation, the European Commission has implemented Europe's Digital Decade policy program, which contains concrete targets and objectives for the year 2030 in areas such as skills, secure and sustainable digital infrastructures, the digital transformation of businesses, and the digitalization of public services. To track the progress in the implementation of the program, the Commission has developed trajectories at the EU level. The baseline trajectories set out how the EU will progress according to the current trends, while the projected trajectories present a path showing annual progress towards the 2030 targets. The difference between the estimated trends and the ideal path will allow the Commission to monitor the gap and make the necessary efforts. Individual EU countries must also prepare their national roadmaps, presenting their approach to achieving Digital Decade's targets (European Parliament and Council, 2022).

Digital transformation is extremely important (Małkowska *et al.*, 2021; Sun *et al.*, 2023b). There is evidence, that the difference in countries' economic performances and their global competitiveness greatly depends on the level of acceptance, availability, and use of ICT, which plays a decisive role in improving almost every aspect of our societies and economies (Borowiecki *et al.*, 2021; Marti & Puertas, 2023). ICT supports new types of interactions, services, and business practices, such as e-commerce, e-government, e-health, e-learning, e-banking, e-finance, freelance, and crowdfunding (Cilan *et al.*, 2009; Selwyn & Facer, 2007; Kovačić *et al.*, 2022; Waliszewski *et al.*, 2023; Piotrowski & Orzeszko, 2023; Wood & Lehdonvirta, 2023). It also accelerates the progress of various transactions, allows to overcome barriers to market access, eliminates spatial constraints, and creates alternative commercial platforms and new industries, that generate new employment opportunities (Vicente & Gil-de-Bernabe, 2010; Vicente & Lopez, 2010; Fuchs & Cumebers, 2023; Su *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, it changes the way people interact with each other, get educated, and obtain information thanks to ICT-based actions and technologies like Internet surfing, YouTube, social networks, online job seeking, email or access to online libraries (Brooks *et al.*, 2005; Szewczyk, 2021; Timotheou *et al.*, 2023).

However, with the rise of the digital economy and society an important and evolving problem, emerging not only in the EU, but also worldwide, has become the digital divide, highlighted in recent years increasingly by several organizations, policymakers, and academics from different fields

(Van Dijk, 2020; Kolupaieva & Tiesheva, 2023). In addition, the coronavirus pandemic has had a huge impact on exposing the enormous importance of this issue. The pandemic has forced people to a unique transformation of their daily living practices while demonstrating even more the phenomenon of digital exclusion resulting from a lack of resources and effective use of digital technologies (De *et al.*, 2020; Aissaoui, 2022; Cramarenco *et al.*, 2023; Żur & Wałęga, 2023).

The digital divide is most interpreted as the gap between individuals, households, businesses, and geographic areas at different socio-economic levels concerning access to, use of, or impact of information and communication technology (ICT) (OECD, 2001; Van Dijk & Hacker, 2003; Aissaoui, 2022; Lythreatis *et al.*, 2022). The Digital Divide is a factor that can exacerbate social and economic inequalities, created by increasing reliance on technology, the Internet, and related solutions (Rogers, 2016; Manduna, 2016; Setthasuravich & Kato, 2020; Ali & Faroque, 2023). It can reduce or improve citizens' social and economic capital and their ability to participate in social and economic life (Ragnedda, 2017; Buffel *et al.*, 2023).

The digital divide, initially understood in a dichotomous way as a state of having or not having access to ICT, is treated today as a complex and multidimensional phenomenon (Cruz-Jesus *et al.*, 2012; Vassilakopoulou & Hustad, 2021). In the spatial context, it is generally considered at two levels: at an international level it reflects differences among different countries, and at an intranational level it results from differences within a single country. However, there are also other geographic divide dimensions considered: among the developed countries, between the developed and developing countries, between the regions, as well as between the rural and urban areas (Holl & Rama, 2023; Chiesa & Rykkja, 2024). Recent literature on the digital divide distinguishes also between three main types of the divide: the access divide associated with access and equipment problems, the usage divide associated with digital literacy, and the performance/capacity divide associated with ICTs including the benefits of using ICTs and more specifically the Internet (Aissaoui, 2022; Merisalo & Makkonen, 2022; Lu *et al.*, 2024; Park & Chun, 2024). It can be concluded that digital gaps between countries, regions, or groups of individuals are caused not only by differences regarding access to the Internet and ICT but also by differences in digital skills and digital usage, conditioned by the presence of specific characteristics, related to different sociodemographic and socio-economic determinants (Hidalgo *et al.*, 2020) or more specific individuals'

characteristics such as motivation, culture or personality (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2014; Helsper, 2021). This underlines that the digital divide is a multifaceted concept covering several aspects (access, use, performance) and which can be analyzed at various levels and in different dimensions (global, national, regional, economic, social, technical, etc.) (Lythreatis *et al.*, 2022).

Understanding the digital divide concept requires an in-depth recognition of the nature, course, and outcomes of digitalization processes, as well as an examination of the specific issues and problems these processes raise. Recently, some publications have reviewed the contributions to digitalization and digital divide literature, which has made significant progress in building an understanding of these phenomena and research undertaken in this area. Part of the reviews have contributed to the discovery of phenomena, definitions, impact factors, or central themes in digitalization research through an explorative process. In this context, the study of Zhu *et al.* (2021) delineated the knowledge flows in research on digital transformation. It identified the most important papers and graphically mapped the influential countries, institutions, and journals. The authors also distinguished the themes of existing research in this area. Hajishirzi *et al.* (2022) identified the major research subjects and components in digital transformation studies to understand how they are related. They found that the key areas in digital transformation studies are the organization, technology, external pressure, people, and perceived benefits and challenges. Vial (2019) on a basis of 282 publications on digital transformations proposed an inductive conceptual framework, summarizing current knowledge on digital transformation, built upon relationships between eight elements describing digital transformation as a process, in which digital technologies play a key role in both, the creation and the reinforcement of disruptions, which take place at the society and industry levels. Verhoef *et al.* (2021) presented a multidisciplinary perspective of studies on digital transformation, identifying the external factors strengthening the need for digital transformation, the phases of digital transformation, and the strategic imperatives of digital transformation. In turn, Hanelt *et al.* (2021) provided a systematic review of the literature on digital transformation, analyzing it from the perspective of organizational change. Their research identified two important thematical patterns: (1) digital transformation is moving companies to malleable organizational designs enabling continuous adaptation, and (2) this movement is embedded in and driven by digital busi-

ness ecosystems. Also, Chen and Shen (2024) provided a systematic overview of research with a focus on digital transformation at the firm level. Its added value was the conceptual framework that can help to better understand the performance of digital transformation in companies from a theoretical perspective, linking corporate digital transformation with dynamic capabilities, digital innovation orientation, and environmental characteristics. The work of Plekhanov *et al.* (2023) supplemented the listed literature reviews by using a new multilevel perspective, considering multiple organizational layers of the firm and its environment, which made it possible to show the complexity of digital transformation-related organizational changes.

In many studies, digital transformation has not been studied as an independent subject and has always been analyzed concerning other concepts like business models or has been studied about a specific industry or sector. This type of review fits the publication of Caputo *et al.* (2021), which provided a comprehensive map of the knowledge structure of the relationship between digitalization and business models, identifying the most influential authors, articles, journals, and research themes in this area. Ching-Hung *et al.* (2021) presented a literature review on digital transformation studies in advanced manufacturing and engineering. This sector is also covered by the publication of Matt *et al.* (2023), in which four thematic areas in industrial digitalization have been identified (technologies, impacts, enabling factors, and barriers) and a meaningful segmentation of the existing publications along these dimensions was included. Other works that can be cited in this context referred, for example, to the education sector and revealed the links between digital transformation and education (Özdemir *et al.*, 2023) or provided a structured overview of Education 4.0-related publications (Mukul & Büyüközkan, 2023). However, it is difficult to find studies that provide valuable results on digitalization research across countries with different levels of socio-economic development. One such example is the publication of Marino-Romero and Folgado-Fernández (2024), who analyzed a total of 164 articles to identify the most relevant publications on digital transformation in developing versus developed countries.

There is much less extensive literature providing an overview of research on the digital divide. Lythreatis *et al.* (2022) in their paper pointed out that since 2017 there have been only two articles in the literature that have summarized research on the digital divide (Aissaoui, 2022; Vass-

ilakopolou & Hustad, 2021), however, the first one covered the studies in one field (Information Systems) and the second one analyzed some determinants of this divide. In this context, Lythreatis *et al.* (2022) identified nine categories of factors that affect the digital divide. Their findings also showed that the digital divide was mostly studied by scholars at an individual, regional, and national level, and the least frequently — at the firm level. They suggested also that in the recent literature, two potential new levels of the digital divide emerged.

The above-mentioned reviews provided valuable insights into state-of-the-art knowledge and future research directions. They have used a bibliometric approach, bringing systematization to digitization-related research and offering a holistic view of this phenomenon, often analyzing it at the level of a single company, or from a perspective that considers multiple organizational layers of the company and its environment. Others derived process (or ‘flow’) models of digital transformation or provided more specialized overviews embedding them in the context of specific issues or sectors of the economy. However, digitization and the associated digital divide are very complex phenomena, and an important determinant influencing them is the socio-economic diversity of the countries to which these studies refer, which has not been sufficiently reflected in mentioned studies.

Our study investigates digitalization trends present in research published over the past five years in European countries, i.e. the EU and Western Balkans (WB) countries, revealing factors that may influence the digital divide. While the EU countries are often seen as more digitally advanced, the WB region, including non-EU countries such as Montenegro, Serbia, Bosnia, Macedonia, Albania, and Kosovo, presents a contrasting landscape that offers valuable insights into digitalization efforts and challenges. The Western Balkan countries hold strategic importance as many of them are in the process of joining the EU. This transition makes their digital transformation particularly relevant, as it reflects their efforts to align with EU standards and policies, which are crucial for their integration and future economic development.

The inclusion of WB countries is essential due to their unique socio-economic contexts and their pivotal role in bridging the digital divide within Europe. By examining these regions, the study aims to understand the factors contributing to the digital divide and the nature of digitalization efforts in diverse socio-economic settings. This comprehensive understand-

ing is vital for formulating effective policies that support digital inclusion and sustainable development not only within the EU, but also in countries aspiring to join the union. This dual perspective enriches the analysis, providing a holistic view of digitalization across varying levels of economic development and integration aspirations, making it both a relevant and compelling area of study for international readers.

The primary aim of this study is to analyze the main characteristics of research conducted on digitalization between 2018 and 2023, comparing the EU and Western Balkan regions. The study seeks to understand the factors contributing to the digital divide and the nature of digitalization efforts in these regions, to provide insights that can inform future research and policy development aimed at enhancing digital inclusion and sustainable development. The following research questions drive our study: What are the main characteristics of the research carried out on digitalization between 2018 and 2023 and the structure of publications from the point of view of the year of publication, the spatial distribution of the research carried out, and the university affiliation, as well as the publication patterns occurring? What are the main dimensions in digitalization that are explored by researchers in EU and WB countries and which digital divide factors and digitalization efforts in these regions do they point to? What are the lessons from this research for shaping more coherent frameworks and policies to address challenges related to digitalization and the digital divide in both regions?

Our study embodies three main contributions. Firstly, it improves the understanding of the theoretical corpus of digitalization research in the past five years and shows the research trends in literature in two distinct groups of countries – in the EU and the Western Balkan region. It allows us to draw conclusions on the scope and nature of research conducted in these groups of countries, as well as to point out similarities and differences between them. It also helps the EU and WB researchers to understand what issues need to be addressed in the future. Secondly, by indicating what digitalization efforts are being made in these regions, we reveal the factors that may be contributing to the digital divide. Digitalization is continuously progressing, thus influencing the evolving concept of the digital divide and its causes, forms, and implications. This review, therefore, allows us to go beyond the current digital divide research framework and to point to possible new aspects of this phenomenon. In this way, it contributes to a better understanding of the digital divide. From this fol-

lows the third contribution, which is support for identifying and developing more coherent frameworks and policies to address this issue to diminish and bridge the digital gap in both regions. This is important in terms of converging the level of digitalization in all countries, as well as supporting WB countries in their integration aspirations.

The study employs a systematic data selection process, choosing Scopus as the database for its extensive coverage of diverse journals. A total of 1119 articles from EU countries and 277 from Western Balkan countries are selected for bibliometric analysis, adhering to PRISMA guidelines. The Scopus database was selected due to its extensive journal coverage, superior citation analysis tools, and user-friendly interface, ensuring a comprehensive and representative dataset. The temporal scope of the bibliographic analysis carried out provided opportunities to assess the research output covering the period before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the detailed methodology used in the study, including the selection criteria and data analysis techniques. Section 3 presents the results of the bibliometric analysis, highlighting key trends and patterns in digitalization research. Section 4 provides a discussion of the findings, comparing the digitalization efforts and challenges in the EU and Western Balkan regions. Finally, Section 5 offers conclusions and recommendations for future research and policy development.

Theoretical background

The role of digitalization in economic and social development

Although there is no unified and overarching definition of digitalization, it can generally be seen as the integration of data and the Internet into production processes, new forms of consumption within households and the public sector, capital formation, cross-border flows, and finance (Borowiecki *et al.*, 2021; Nadoleanu *et al.*, 2022). Progressive digital transformation is commonly cited as the foundation of growth in the twenty-first century (Małkowska *et al.*, 2021; Kolupaieva & Tiesheva, 2023; Özdemir *et al.*, 2023). The information and communication technology (ICT) sector plays a particular role in this regard. The global ICT market, one of the largest industries, is forecast to reach a size of 6 trillion EUR in 2023. How-

ever, the EU's position in the global ecosystem is not the best. It is deteriorating — the EU's share in global revenues on the ICT market has decreased dramatically over the last decade, including from 21.8% in 2013 to 11.3% in 2022, while the US share increased from 26.8% to 36,0% (European Commission, 2023).

The discussion about the course, effects, and challenges of digitalization has been going on for years, involving scientists, political decision-makers, consulting companies, and international organizations (European Commission, 2019; OECD, 2019; Stankovic *et al.*, 2021; Hanelt, 2021; UN, 2021). Various aspects of the impact of digitalization on enterprises, economy, society, or institutions are recognized (Tiutiunyk *et al.*, 2021; Turek *et al.*, 2023; Guandalini, 2022). Research shows that the digital economy is the main element of transformation in many countries (Yu *et al.*, 2023). On the one hand, it creates new opportunities for solving existing problems, but on the other, it also brings several challenges. It is claimed that the impact of the broadly understood digital transformation on the economy and society results from the structural changes in the operating model of enterprises, economy, and society that are its consequence (Matthess & Kunkel, 2020). Researchers investigate how countries and supranational organizations, such as the European Union, reshape their traditional economic and social landscapes by i.e. promoting broadband use and internet usage, delivering online services for citizens, facilitating investments related to different aspects of the digital economy and society, as well as implementing new business models appropriate for digital economy development (Laitsou *et al.*, 2020; Horobet *et al.*, 2023; Pinto *et al.*, 2023).

ICT is a new general-purpose technology that has a broad and deep impact on the economy, generating a wide range of new products, production processes, and services, as well as giving rise to new industries, both in the manufacturing and service sectors (Lewandowska *et al.*, 2023). Due to its vast and diverse impact on various economic sectors, such as agriculture, industry, trade, education, health, transport, and many others, the digital economy is perceived as one of the most important factors for the growth, development, and prosperity of countries, supporting job creation work, entrepreneurship, and innovation (Jamil, 2021; Oloyede, 2023). It is indicated that this is a factor that has allowed many countries, such as China, to transform into one of the largest economies in the world (Wu & Yu, 2022). Digitalization contributes to changing the structure of the economy by in-

creasing the share of the digital economy in GDP, thus supporting economic growth (Zhang *et al.*, 2022; Myovella *et al.*, 2020).

Many studies have also demonstrated how the digital economy can effectively empower enterprises by supporting the production of higher-quality goods and services at reduced costs (Karlsson *et al.*, 2008; Zeng & Lei, 2021; Piotrowski & Orzeszko, 2023), changing the way companies do business and interact with customers and suppliers (Fröhlich & Steinbiß, 2020; Nambisan, 2017; Sun *et al.*, 2022b), introducing new business models and creating innovations (Audretsch *et al.*, 2016; Lewandowska *et al.*, 2023), as well as raising the efficiency of processes and increasing productivity (Bouwman *et al.*, 2019; Khalil *et al.*, 2022; Civelek *et al.*, 2023). It was also evidenced that digitalization facilitates access to new markets and new customers around the world, leading to an increase in exports (Dethine *et al.*, 2020) and supporting professional activity in the labor market thanks to remote work and distance education (Urbaniec & Źmija, 2022). Numerous studies also concern the determinants of digitalization. In this line of research Ershova *et al.*, claim that the development of the digital economy depends on public policy, strategic planning, digital transformation monitoring, effective and efficient leadership, proper institutions, effective legal framework, human capital development, research, development, and innovation, enabling business environment, as well as digital infrastructure (Ershova *et al.*, 2018).

Numerous studies in the literature explore the issues related to a digital society which can be defined as “a modern, progressive society that is formed because of the adoption and integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) at home, work, education and recreation, and supported by advanced telecommunications and wireless connectivity systems and solutions (Sandulescu Budea, 2021). There is an extensive body of publications studying how digitalization can benefit society, for example through providing easy access to public services (Latupeirissa *et al.*, 2024), better employment opportunities (Ključnikov *et al.*, 2023), and greater economic growth, which can lead to well-being (Galindo-Martín *et al.*, 2019; Kryzhanovskij *et al.*, 2021; Vanden Abeele & Nguyen, 2022). Nevertheless, in the digital context, adverse negative effects on society may also occur.

In general, digitalization provides individuals with opportunities for a paradigm shift in development, but there is an imbalance in the distribution of the digital dividend. Analyzing the digital transformation of the

countries and the existing digital divide many studies confirm that the effects of the spread of digital technologies are greater in more developed, high- and middle-income countries, while in developing, low-income countries, which often face additional problems, such as inappropriate government policy, low level of infrastructure development or competence of digital citizens, various specific challenges arise (Kolupaieva & Tiesheva, 2023; Lythreathis *et al.*, 2022; Marti & Puertas, 2023). The existence of significant disparities between and within countries in access to and use of ICT may hinder the achievement of sustainable development goals, such as economic growth, decent work, well-being, and the reduction of poverty (Jamil, 2020). To take this aspect into account, we conduct a bibliographic analysis drawing conclusions resulting from the research for countries characterized by diverse socio-economic settings.

The place of digitalization in the EU policy

Digital transformation is one of the key elements of the EU's socio-economic development (Tutak & Brodny, 2022). That's why the EU is working on a range of issues to support Europe's digital future. Already in 2010, in line with the Lisbon Strategy, the 10-year Digital Agenda for Europe identified for the first time the key role of ICT in achieving Europe's goals (European Commission, 2010). In 2015, the Digital Single Market Strategy developed the Digital Agenda, focusing it on three pillars aimed at ensuring a fair, open, and secure digital environment, providing better access to digital goods and services for consumers and businesses, creating appropriate conditions for the development of digital networks and services and maximizing the growth potential of the digital economy. In 2020, the second five-year digital strategy — Shaping Europe's Digital Future — was launched focusing on three key digital goals: technology that works for people, a fair and competitive economy, and an open, democratic, and sustainable society (European Commission, 2020). In 2021, the strategy was reinforced with the 10-year Digital Compass: Europe's Path to the Digital Decade, which concretes the EU's digital ambitions for 2030, setting four digital targets related to skills, businesses, infrastructure, and public services (European Commission, 2021a). The Digital Decade policy program 2030 is based on an annual cooperation mechanism involving the Commission and Member States, consisting of:

- monitoring of annual progress in achieving each of the 2030 goals, based on the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI),
- an annual report prepared by the Commission, including the evaluation of progress and recommendations for actions,
- Digital Decade strategic roadmaps, in which member states present adopted or planned actions to achieve the 2030 goals (prepared every two years)
- the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium, which is a mechanism to support the implementation of multi-country projects.

In addition, in 2021 the Digital Europe program was established – a new EU digital financing program with a planned total budget of EUR 7.5 billion for the years 2021–2027, which will provide strategic financing for projects in five areas: supercomputing, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, advanced digital skills and ensuring the broad use of digital technologies across the economy and society (European Parliament, 2021).

The current EU's digital strategy has a very wide scope and covers many key issues, the most important of which are (European Council, Council of the European Union):

- The Digital Decade – a governance framework to achieve the 2030 digital goals,
- Declaration of Digital Rights and Principles – defining citizens' rights in the digital space and creating a framework of principles that the EU and Member States agree to follow during the digital transformation,
- Digital services – the EU legal framework for digital services,
- Data-driven economy – the European data strategy that will create a single data market that is consistent with common EU values and allows data to be shared and reused more widely across sectors and countries,
- Taxation of digital activities – the legal framework adapting the tax systems of EU countries to the requirements of the digital era,
- Artificial intelligence – establishing a comprehensive and future-proof European legal framework of ethical principles for the development, deployment, and use of AI, robotics, and related technologies,
- Connectivity – developing harmonized regulations for connectivity services in the EU,
- Cybersecurity – EU cybersecurity strategy, increasing Europe's resilience to cyber threats and ensuring that all citizens and businesses can benefit from trusted digital tools and services,

- European Digital Identity (eID) – EU-wide framework for a secure public electronic identity,
- Digitalization of the justice system – digitalization of Member States' judicial systems, expanding access to justice for citizens and companies and increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of court proceedings,
- Digital information exchange – increasing the exchange of digital information between national authorities and Eurojust in terrorism cases.

Success in achieving the Digital Decade goals will be crucial for the EU's future prosperity and will require a significant acceleration and deepening of action by Member States to reform and improve the business environment, as well as to create incentives and boost investment in digital technologies, skills, and infrastructure. In parallel, the EU supports the Western Balkan countries in their digitalization efforts, which is reflected in the launch of a Digital Agenda for the Western Balkans, which is one of the six main initiatives of the Western Balkans strategy. Digital Agenda for the Western Balkans aims to support the digital transition of the region and sets out five main areas to be covered: (1) investing in broadband connectivity, (2) increasing cybersecurity, trust, and digitalization of industry, (3) strengthening the digital economy and society and (4) boosting research and innovation (Zuzaku & Abazi, 2022).

The European strategies and recommendations intend to increase the level of digitalization and to narrow digital disparities, achieving similar conduct between and within countries, but there is still work to be done. Comparative analyses with global peers indicate that the EU is lagging in certain aspects of digitalization. For instance, a study by Myovella *et al.* (2020) shows that while the EU has strong regulatory frameworks, it trails behind the US and China in areas such as artificial intelligence and 5G deployment. The EU's slower pace in adopting these technologies can be attributed to regulatory complexities and fragmented markets.

Moreover, even though at the EU and individual member states' level, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, many legislative documents have been developed and adopted to regulate digitalization issues, it turns out that many countries were not and still are not prepared for the challenges that digitalization entails. Despite many support measures, numerous reports and studies presenting the digitalization progress of EU member states, including those with EU candidate status, point to the digital development disparities that exist and have been widening in some respects (Borowiecki *et al.*, 2021; Małkowska *et al.*, 2021; Kolupaieva &

Tiesheva, 2023; Pinto *et al.*, 2023; Horobet *et al.*, 2023; Sati, 2024). Also, the European Commission's DESI reports highlight that although the EU has made significant strides in digitalization, disparities among member states remain a challenge. Northern and Western European countries typically outperform their Southern and Eastern counterparts in digital skills, internet use, and integration of digital technology (European Commission, 2021b).

Tiutiunyk *et al.* (2023) point to some economic impacts of rapid digitalization in developing countries (significant decrease in GDP, bankruptcy of entities, especially SMEs) as well as social impacts (reduced living standards, deterioration of social security). Citizens and businesses of countries characterized by low levels of digital literacy are not ready for a rapid reorientation of their lives and activities, which leads to economic and social losses at micro and macro levels (Vrchota *et al.*, 2020; Siuta-Tokarska, 2021; Antonijević *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, some studies indicate that countries classified as digital access leaders (with advanced digital infrastructure and high levels of digital access) may also have an imbalance or underperformance in terms of digitalization related to the uptake of digital technologies in the business sector. They point to a potential gap between digital infrastructure and the extent to which companies have adopted and integrated digital technologies. While citizens are supported in providing digital access by public investment, businesses may not have the necessary infrastructure or resources to implement it effectively (Pinto *et al.*, 2023; OECD, 2021). Research by Laitso *et al.* (2020) emphasizes the role of broadband penetration and digital skill enhancement in driving economic growth and reducing inequality within the EU. The study suggests that targeted investments in these areas can help bridge the digital divide, particularly in less developed regions.

The above-outlined problems further highlight the need for better recognition of the digitalization phenomenon to reduce the digital divide that is evident in various aspects of the socio-economic life in European countries having different socio-economic conditions. By identifying the factors that contribute to both the digitization and digital divide, policymakers can develop targeted strategies to bridge this gap. Understanding the nuances of a country's digital performance in different regions enables policymakers to design context-specific policies that address unique challenges and opportunities.

Methods

To assemble a robust dataset, various bibliometric databases housing scholarly papers were considered. After careful evaluation, the Scopus database was chosen for its extensive coverage, multidisciplinary scope, and international representation of scholarly works. While both Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) are commonly used for bibliometric analyses, Scopus was selected for several compelling reasons that align with the objectives of this study.

Scopus covers a larger number of journals and includes a more extensive range of international publications compared to WoS. According to Asubiaro *et al.* (2024), Scopus offers broader journal coverage and includes a more diverse range of disciplines, particularly beneficial for capturing comprehensive bibliometric data across various fields. This extensive coverage ensures a more representative dataset, capturing a wide array of research outputs from both developed and developing regions.

Scopus provides superior tools for analyzing citations and includes a more extensive citation network. This is particularly important for our study, which aims to analyze citation patterns and research impact. Asubiaro *et al.* (2024) highlight that Scopus's citation analysis capabilities are robust, allowing for detailed insights into the influence and reach of publications related to digitalization.

Scopus has a more user-friendly interface and provides more flexibility in refining and exporting data for bibliometric analysis. This ease of use is critical for ensuring accurate and efficient data extraction and analysis, which is essential for maintaining methodological rigor. Prancutė (2021) emphasizes the user-friendly nature of Scopus and its comprehensive bibliometric tools, making it a preferred choice for complex bibliometric analyses.

On the positive aspects of the proposed methodology, we have identified:

- Scopus covers a larger number of journals and disciplines, ensuring a comprehensive dataset.
- Scopus provides robust tools for analyzing citation patterns, offering detailed insights into research impact.
- The interface is intuitive and flexible, facilitating accurate and efficient data extraction and analysis.

On the other hand, potential negative aspects could be:

- The choice of Scopus may introduce bias as it may over-represent certain disciplines or regions.
- By not including data from other sources, the study may miss relevant publications that are indexed in other databases, potentially affecting the comprehensiveness of the analysis.
- Any inherent limitations of the Scopus database, such as coverage gaps in specific areas, could impact the study's findings.

On November 23, 2023, we performed a data download from the Scopus database, utilizing specific search terms to focus on relevant content. The initial search utilized the keyword 'digit*' to capture a broad range of articles related to digitalization, including those that address the digital divide within the broader context of digital transformation. This inclusive approach ensures that relevant studies on digital inclusion, digital literacy, and other related aspects are not excluded. For the EU dataset, the search query 'digit*' AND 'EU' was used to capture articles discussing digitalization in the context of the European Union policies and regional strategies. This search utilized listed keywords in the searchable fields for article title, abstract, and keywords, yielding a substantial set of 4116 records.

Similarly, the outlined methodology was replicated for the Western Balkan countries, encompassing Montenegro, Serbia, Bosnia, Macedonia, Albania, and Kosovo. The inclusion of the WB countries is essential due to their distinct socio-economic characteristics, their strategic geopolitical importance, and their ongoing process of the EU integration. These countries are at a critical juncture where aligning their digital infrastructure and policies with the EU standards is vital for their future economic and political stability. Studying these countries provides a contrasting perspective that highlights the challenges and opportunities in less digitally developed regions, allowing for a deeper analysis of the digital divide.

The Western Balkan countries' efforts in digital transformation are not only significant for their national development, but also for the broader European context. As they strive to bridge the digital gap, their progress offers valuable lessons and insights that can inform policies and strategies aimed at achieving digital inclusivity across Europe. The search query applied to the Scopus database targeted articles with the keywords "digit*" AND "Montenegro OR Serbia OR Bosnia OR Macedonia OR Albania OR Kosovo" appearing in the article title, abstract, or keywords. This focused search strategy resulted in the retrieval of 1121 records in our dataset. The

observed dataset is freely available at Zenodo (Kovač, 2023). This approach ensures a region-specific examination, allowing us to discern trends and developments related to digital topics within the context of the Western Balkan countries. The consistent application of the Scopus database and the tailored search criteria maintains methodological rigor and comparability across different geographical scopes, fostering a comprehensive analysis of the digital landscape.

To ensure the quality and consistency of the dataset, a comprehensive cleaning process was carried out. This included standardizing keywords to avoid duplications and inconsistencies. For instance, singular and plural versions of the same keyword were standardized to a single term to ensure uniformity. Similar standardizations were applied to other synonyms and variations of terms to maintain consistency across the dataset. However, it is important to note that the presence of such variations does not substantially affect the overall analysis. These instances were relatively few and were addressed appropriately during the data-cleaning process.

This method ensures a comprehensive and representative dataset, capturing the multifaceted nature of digitalization and its impact on the digital divide.

To streamline both datasets and ensure precision in our analysis, we employed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework. This systematic approach aids in refining the dataset by applying rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria, facilitating a more focused examination of pertinent scientific literature.

Sources of data and procedure

PRISMA is a set of guidelines developed to improve the transparency, completeness, and quality of reporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses. It has become widely recognized and endorsed within the scientific community as a valuable tool for promoting the transparency and reliability of systematic review reporting. PRISMA was established to address the growing need for a standardized approach to presenting the findings of systematic reviews, which are critical tools in evidence-based practice and research synthesis. By adhering to the PRISMA guidelines, we aimed to enhance the credibility and utility of our systematic review.

To facilitate separate comparisons between countries associated with the European Union (EU) and those outside the EU, we categorized Euro-

pean countries into two distinct sets. The first set comprises countries already within the EU, including Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden. The second set consists of countries in the Western Balkan region, namely Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia. This division enables a focused analysis of research trends and outcomes in these distinct geographical clusters.

Research began with two datasets: one related to the EU, containing 4116 records, and the other related to the Western Balkan countries with 1121 rows. Both datasets were subjected to the PRISMA methodology, implemented using Python. As is presented in Figure 1, the PRISMA methodology consists of a structured approach involving four key steps: identification, screening, eligibility, and reporting.

Upon observation, it was identified that due to co-authorship, certain records were duplicated in both datasets. Consequently, the initial step involved reducing the number of records in the EU dataset. After detecting and addressing 38 duplicates, the EU dataset was refined, resulting in a total of 4078 records.

To focus exclusively on scientific papers, we refined the dataset by including only articles. This additional restriction led to a further reduction in the dataset, resulting in 2430 rows for the EU dataset, comprising only articles, and 659 rows for the Western Balkan (WB) dataset. Subsequently, our analysis specifically targeted recent articles, limiting the timeframe to those published in the last five years, spanning from 2018 to 2023. Within this temporal scope, we obtained 444 rows about the WB countries and 1695 for EU countries.

Finally, to underscore the research significance of the records in the dataset, we opted to include only those with at least one citation. This refinement resulted in a dataset comprising 1119 rows for the EU and 277 rows for the WB countries. The subsequent plots will delve into the analysis of these newly formed datasets.

The consistent application of the Scopus database and the tailored search criteria maintain methodological rigor and comparability across different geographical scopes, fostering a comprehensive analysis of the digital landscape. By including the WB countries, the study not only addresses a gap in the literature but also contributes to a more complete un-

derstanding of digitalization in Europe, making the findings highly relevant for international readers interested in regional development, the EU integration, and digital policy.

Results

Documents by year

In the EU dataset, the number of articles with more than zero citations has exhibited an upward trend over the observed years. In 2018, there were 99 such articles, followed by increases in subsequent years, reaching 147 in 2019, 223 in 2020, 250 in 2021, 257 in 2022, and 143 in 2023. This suggests a general rise in the impact and visibility of scholarly publications, with a peak in 2022 (see Figure 2.).

Turning to the WB countries, a similar positive trend is observed, albeit with lower absolute numbers. In 2018, there were 21 articles with more than zero citations, which increased to 36 in 2019, 59 in 2020, 65 in 2021, 74 in 2022, and 22 in 2023. Although the numbers are smaller compared to the EU dataset, the trend remains consistent, indicating a growth in the impact and citation rates of articles from Western Balkan countries. The parallel trends across both datasets suggest a shared trajectory in the increasing recognition of scholarly work, reflecting a broader engagement and influence of research from both the EU and Western Balkan regions.

Interestingly, a notable observation in both datasets is a decrease in the number of articles with more than zero citations in the year 2023 compared to the previous years (the analysis covered 10.5 months of 2023). While the trend in the EU dataset showed a decline from 257 articles in 2022 to 143 articles in 2023, the Western Balkan dataset similarly experienced a drop from 74 articles in 2022 to 22 articles in 2023. This decline in 2023 might suggest a unique influence, possibly related to external factors such as the past global COVID-19 pandemic. It appears that the years heavily impacted by the pandemic, notably 2020 and 2021, were more fruitful in terms of research output. However, it should be kept in mind that 2023 is not yet over and the final number of digitalization publications this year is likely to be higher.

Documents by country

The data on the number of articles with more than zero citations in the EU and the WB, countries reveal interesting trends, as is shown in Figure 3. In the EU, the top 10 countries contributing to research output are led by Spain with 160 articles, followed closely by Italy with 148 articles, and Germany with 105 articles. Other notable contributors include the Netherlands, Belgium, Poland, Romania, France, Portugal, and Greece.

In the Western Balkan countries, the distribution is more varied. Serbia emerges as the leading contributor with a substantial 131 articles. Other countries, such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, Montenegro, and North Macedonia, also contribute significantly, with citation counts ranging from 11 to 33 articles.

A comparative analysis of these trends suggests that certain EU countries have higher individual research outputs compared to the combined research outputs of multiple Western Balkan countries. However, the presence of the leading contributor like Serbia in the Western Balkans indicates a concentration of research activity in specific countries within the region. These insights can inform discussions on collaborative research efforts and potential areas for further exploration.

Croatia and Slovenia, although geographically located in the Balkan region, have already become integral members of the EU. When considering its research output within the EU context, Croatia stands at the 13th position with 31 articles, showcasing a competitive presence in EU research endeavors. On the other hand, Slovenia occupies the 22nd place with 17 articles, reflecting a slightly lower research output compared to some other EU member states.

These rankings emphasize the diverse contributions of EU member countries, with Croatia demonstrating a competitive standing and Slovenia still making notable contributions, albeit at a somewhat lower scale. The inclusion of Croatia and Slovenia in the EU research landscape underscores the collaborative and integrated nature of scientific endeavors within the European Union. Further analysis of the factors influencing research productivity in these countries could provide valuable insights into the dynamics of scientific collaboration and innovation within the EU framework.

The observed disparity in research output among WB countries, with Serbia emerging as a leading contributor, may be attributed to various fac-

tors. One plausible explanation is the demographic aspect, as Serbia has a larger population compared to other countries in the region. A larger population often translates into a greater pool of researchers and, consequently, a higher research output.

However, it's essential to consider other factors that contribute to this phenomenon. The concentration of research activity in Serbia could also indicate a higher level of investment in research and development within the country. Governments and institutions in Serbia may have prioritized and allocated resources to foster a robust research environment, leading to increased scholarly contributions.

This observation underscores the multifaceted nature of research disparities, incorporating demographic factors, investment in research infrastructure, and strategic policy decisions. Further exploration into these factors could provide valuable insights for policymakers, funding agencies, and researchers seeking to enhance research collaboration and productivity across the Western Balkan region.

Documents by affiliations

The university affiliation counts for EU countries showcase (see Figure 4.) the distribution of research articles among various universities in the dataset. Notably, the University of Craiova takes the lead with 16 articles, emphasizing its significant role in contributing to scientific knowledge. Following closely are the University of Amsterdam and the West University of Timisoara, each with 11 and 10 articles, respectively. Other prominent institutions include the Bucharest University of Economic Studies, the Silesian University of Technology, and the University of Zagreb. This analysis provides valuable insights into the research output of these universities, highlighting their diverse contributions and underlining the collaborative nature of the academic sector within the European Union.

A surprising observation in the university affiliation counts for EU countries is the absence of universities with many articles, indicating a diffuse distribution of research efforts across various institutions. This can indicate that themes related to digitalization are not frequently chosen by researchers. The absence of universities with a substantial number of articles in this domain suggests that the digital gap may not be the primary focus of academic research within the European Union. This observation raises questions about the level of attention and priority given to issues

surrounding digital disparities in the academic community. The diffuse distribution of research across various institutions further emphasizes the need to encourage and promote more studies in this critical area to better understand and address the challenges posed by the digital divide in the European context.

Figure 5. illustrates the distribution of research articles across various universities in WB countries. The dataset includes the count of articles associated with each university, providing insights into the research output of academic institutions in the region. Notably, the University of Belgrade emerges as the leading contributor with 58 articles, followed by the University of Novi Sad with 35 articles. Other universities, such as the University of Sarajevo, the University of Montenegro, and the University of Prishtina, also make significant contributions, highlighting the diverse academic landscape in the Western Balkans.

The University of Belgrade and the University of Novi Sad, both situated in Serbia, stand out as significantly more productive in publishing scientific research compared to other universities in the Western Balkan region (as well as in the EU). This notable gap in productivity among Western Balkan universities underscores the need for fostering stronger research collaborations and networks within the region. Establishing more robust connections between scientists from leading institutions, such as the University of Belgrade and the University of Novi Sad, with researchers from less active universities could prove beneficial. Moreover, bridging the gap between Western Balkan institutions and those at the forefront of scientific advancements in the European Union could contribute to a more cohesive and collaborative research environment, ultimately addressing shared challenges and fostering academic excellence across the region.

Documents by source

The top journals in the datasets for both the EU and the WB countries provide valuable insights into the research focus areas and publication patterns within these regions (see Figure 6). For the EU dataset, the most popular journal is "Sustainability (Switzerland)" with a substantial count of 57 articles. This suggests a prevalent emphasis on sustainability-related topics within EU research. Other prominent journals include "Energies" and "Computer Law and Security Review," indicating a diverse range of

research interests, spanning energy-related studies and legal aspects of computer security.

In the Western Balkan dataset, the journal "Sustainability" also takes the lead with 16 articles, showcasing a shared interest in sustainability research with the EU. "Tehnički vjesnik" and "Business Systems Research" hold multiple articles, indicating a focus on technical and business-related subjects. Notably, "Education Sciences" and "Serbian Journal of Management" contribute to the diversity of research topics within the WB dataset.

A commonality between the two regions is the prominence of "Sustainability" reflecting a shared emphasis on sustainable development and environmental considerations. However, it is important to note the publishing policy of "Sustainability." As an open-access journal, "Sustainability" publishes many papers each year. While this ensures wide accessibility and rapid dissemination of research findings, it also raises concerns about the journal's selectivity and the overall quality of the published articles. The high volume of publications can lead to perceptions of lower rigor compared to journals with more restrictive publishing practices.

The open-access model of "Sustainability" allows for increased visibility and citation potential, which likely contributes to its high number of publications and citations observed. However, researchers and policymakers should consider the implications of this model when interpreting the bibliometric data. The scale of the journal's output can significantly influence the overall publication and citation patterns within the field, and the sheer volume of articles may affect the perceived impact and quality.

These important parameters play a crucial role in shaping the preferences of researchers and scholars when selecting journals for publication. The widespread adoption of "Sustainability" in both datasets suggests that researchers in the EU and WB value these characteristics, aligning with the journal's commitment to fostering impactful and accessible research in various scientific domains. Additionally, both datasets encompass a mix of journals covering diverse fields, ranging from technology and agriculture to law and education. These insights underscore the multidisciplinary nature of research in both the EU and the Western Balkans, highlighting the collaborative efforts and varied interests of researchers across different domains within these regions.

Keywords networks

Figure 7. shows the proportion of keywords related to sustainable development, adult education, and economic and social consequences in the European Union. Most keywords (37.7%) focus on the European Union, indicating extensive research on these topics in Europe. Other important keywords include “human” (11.0%), “humans” (7.2%), “digital storage” (7.1%), and “economic and social effects” (4.7%). These keywords reflect a growing interest in the relationship between sustainable development and the economy and society in Europe.

Figure 8. shows the percentage of different studies observed in Western Balkan countries. Serbia has the largest share (12.0%), indicating its leading role in the research domain. Bosnia and Herzegovina have the next largest share (5.3%), followed by Greece (4.8%), Kosovo (3.7%), and Albania (3.5%) showing that research is focused on topics and questions related mainly to the local regions. These countries are all involved in research but to a lesser extent than Serbia. The pie chart also indicates that the latest research in the Western Balkans is focusing on topics that include the word female (11.8%) and to a smaller extent the word male (10.2%).

Figure 8 underscores the predominant research focus of WB countries on societal inquiries, with a particular emphasis on the electronic domain, including remote sensing. The pronounced concentration on countries within the region, such as Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Albania, emphasizes a localized approach to addressing societal challenges. The research also displays a gender-diverse nature, evident in the significant appearance of the words “female” and “male”. This trend indicates an exploration of gender-specific roles and contributions within research domains in the Western Balkans. The research exhibits a focus on the middle-aged demographic, suggesting an orientation toward societal domains, given the typical engagement of this age group in the labor force. Further investigation into these trends could yield valuable insights into the intersectionality of gender, age, and research focus in the region.

Figure 9. shows that the most common keyword related to digital EU data is “digital storage” (41.7%). This implies that digital storage is a significant focus of research and discussion on digital EU data. Other notable keywords include “digitization” (12.3%), “digitalization” (8.6%), “digital transformation” (6.7%), “digital technologies” (5.5%), and “digital divide” (5.5%). These keywords suggest that there is a wide range of research on

digital EU data, covering topics such as the economic and social impacts of digitalization, the development and use of digital technologies, and the storage and management of digital data.

Figure 10. illustrates the primary keyword associated with digital web data in Western Balkan countries as “digital storage” (22.2%), indicating the significant emphasis on the digital divide in research and discussion. Additional noteworthy keywords comprise “digital elevation model” (20.0%), “digital mapping” (8.9%), and “digitization” (6.7%), illustrating a wide range of topics encompassing the impact of the digital web on society, the utilization of digital technologies for marketing and business, and the storage and management of digital web data.

Examining digital data-related keywords in the EU (Figure 9) and WB (Figure 10) reveals distinct areas of focus. In the EU, “digital storage” takes precedence (41.7%), emphasizing the significance of storage infrastructure in discussions around digital EU data. Additional keywords like “digitization”, “digitalization”, and “digital transformation” underscore the multifaceted nature of research, covering economic and social impacts, technological advancements, and data management. The WB region places a notable emphasis on the digital domain, particularly digital storage, which stands out as the primary keyword (22.2%). The research in WB countries exhibits a well-distributed focus, with almost equal percentages dedicated to themes such as the “digital elevation model”. This signifies a balanced exploration of societal impact, business applications, and data management within the digital web domain.

In comparison, the EU demonstrates a distinct research landscape, with almost half of the research dedicated to “digital storage” and “digitization”. The higher percentage allocated to digital storage in the EU suggests a heightened focus on data management, while the emphasis on digitization indicates a comprehensive exploration of the broader societal and economic impacts of digital technologies. These observations underscore the different research priorities in the EU and WB regions, with both regions exploring the multifaceted dimensions of the digital landscape while allocating emphasis differently across specific themes.

The final datasets for the EU and WB regions, obtained through the application of the PRISMA selection methodology, were subjected to in-depth analysis using Visualization of Similarities Viewer (VOSviewer) software. VOSviewer is a tool used for creating and visualizing bibliometric overlays, which are graphical representations of the relationships between items,

such as documents, authors, or keywords. In the ensuing visualizations, each node's size corresponds to its frequency of occurrence within the datasets. The connecting curves between nodes denote their co-occurrence in the same publication. The proximity of nodes on the plot reflects the strength of the co-occurrence relationship, with shorter distances indicating a higher frequency of shared occurrence between two keywords. This approach provides a comprehensive and visually interpretable representation of the relationships and patterns within the selected datasets, highlighting the significant themes and interconnections present in the research landscape of the EU and WB regions.

The conclusive datasets, comprising 277 rows for the WB and 1119 rows for the EU, underwent thorough analysis using VOSviewer, employing the entire spectrum of keywords as defined by the authors. The analysis adhered to specific settings tailored for each region. In the EU dataset, a minimum keyword occurrence threshold of 5 was set, resulting in 118 keywords meeting the established criterion out of a total of 3880 keywords. On the other hand, the WB dataset employed a minimum keyword occurrence threshold of 3, leading to 50 keywords meeting the threshold out of the initial 1116 keywords. Four keywords were identified as disconnected and subsequently eliminated from the analysis, leaving a total of 46 connected keywords for further exploration in the research landscape of the Western Balkans. These carefully chosen thresholds ensure a focused and meaningful exploration of the keyword co-occurrence patterns within the datasets.

As shown in Figure 11., in the EU-related dataset, a total of 118 keywords have been categorized into 8 clusters, with the largest cluster comprising 19 keywords. This prominent cluster is centered around key themes such as digital economy, digital transformation, digitalization, sustainable development, economic growth, and innovation. The cohesiveness of these keywords within a substantial cluster suggests a significant focus on the intersection of digital technologies, economic advancements, and sustainable development in the research landscape.

The exploration of digitalization within the European Union is multifaceted, involving synergies with various critical domains. In this analysis, digitalization is intricately linked with key areas such as the digital divide, artificial intelligence, blockchain, the impact of COVID-19, education, and the single digital market. The examination extends to include the DESI index in conjunction with aspects like digital skills, e-commerce, and economic growth. Furthermore, the study delves into the digital divide, with

a specific focus on dimensions such as digital literacy, digital competence, social media, internet accessibility, and e-government. This comprehensive approach underscores the interconnected nature of digitalization, considering both its broad implications and specific facets within the European context.

Within the WB dataset, comprising 46 keywords, the identified terms are categorized into 7 clusters based on their interconnections, as is shown in Figure 12. The largest cluster, encompassing 12 items, revolves around the term COVID-19 and prominently explores topics related to education and learning. This cluster includes keywords such as students, teachers, education, online learning, media, digital skills, media literacy, as well as the term Serbia. Similarly, clusters associated with the terms Montenegro and Albania delve into comparable themes, incorporating elements like pandemic, skills, and innovation. Another cluster focuses on digitization within the context of business, entailing terms like sustainability, entrepreneurship, industry 4.0, and digital platforms. Digital technologies are further explored in the domain of e-education and the Internet. Notably, research in Bosnia and Herzegovina centers around GIS technologies, digital elevation models, and spatial distribution studies.

Examining Figure 12 provides a clear understanding that the WB region exhibits a significant emphasis on digitization in education, driven by the impact of the coronavirus pandemic and the shift to unconventional teaching methods. Moreover, there is a notable focus on studying digitization in the domain of business, reflecting regional aspirations for the modernization of business processes and enhancement of economic infrastructure. While the WB region demonstrates relative cohesion in terms of research, there is evident stratification of topics at the level of individual countries within the region.

Overlay visualization

The overlay view in VOSviewer enriches the exploration of intricate networks by integrating supplementary information through color-coded nodes, fostering a detailed comprehension of the underlying data. The indicator denotes the current publications, transitioning from purple to yellow. Blue keywords signify an earlier appearance compared to yellow ones. The size of the circles corresponds to the frequency of keyword appearance, while the distance between circles reflects their correlation.

The network map (see Figures 13. and 14.) delineates trend topics based on keywords utilized between January 2018 and November 2023. Evolving away from the digital single market, copyright, higher education, fake news, and online platforms, recent studies in the EU demonstrate a heightened focus on the circular economy, digital sovereignty, internet governance, digital policy, strategic autonomy, and panel data (see Figure 13.).

As indicated in Figure 14, initially, during the period from 2018 to 2023 in WB countries, the research primarily centered around COVID-19. However, as time progressed, there was a shift in focus towards online learning, the pandemic, and media. In the most recent period, the research has prominently highlighted topics related to digital transformations, specifically in digital marketing, e-learning, and higher education, as well as firm performance, particularly in the context of innovation and entrepreneurship.

These trends likely mirror the broader global context, where societies and economies are navigating the multifaceted impacts of technological advancements, public health challenges, and the evolving digital landscape. The observed shift in research focus in the EU and WB countries over the period considered can be attributed to dynamic changes in societal and technological landscapes. In the EU, the heightened attention to circular economy, digital sovereignty, internet governance, digital policy, strategic autonomy, and panel data suggests an adaptation to evolving priorities and challenges. In WB countries, the initial emphasis on COVID-19 reflects the immediate response to a global crisis. The subsequent shift towards online learning, the pandemic, and media suggests a continuous adaptation to changing circumstances and evolving research needs. The increased focus on digital transformations, encompassing digital marketing, e-learning, higher education, and firm performance, signals a recognition of the growing significance of digital technologies in shaping various aspects of the business landscape governed by national strategies influenced by the Smart Specialization Strategy (S3).

Density visualization

VOSviewer's density visualization is a graphical representation that provides insights into the concentration and distribution of keywords or elements within a network. The density visualization assigns varying shades or colors to different regions of the network, indicating the level of density or interconnectedness. Higher density implies that keywords in

a particular region are more interconnected, forming a cluster of related terms. Darker or more intense colors represent areas with higher density, while lighter or less intense colors indicate less interconnected regions. Density visualizations depicting the distribution of keywords in the analyzed EU and WB datasets are presented in Figures 15. and 16., respectively.

Analyzing the density visualization of the EU dataset in VOSviewer reveals that key influencers shaping the clustering of the EU datasets primarily include "European Union" and "COVID-19," followed by "digitalization," "digital transformation," "GDPR," and "artificial intelligence." While other themes or elements may appear in the research, their involvement in forming patterns, trends, and relationships within the dataset is comparatively lesser.

In alignment with the EU dataset, the WB dataset exhibits a significant research emphasis on COVID-19-related themes, as can be viewed in Figure 16. Additionally, the research is concentrated in the domains of digitalization, digital marketing, digital transformation, and digital technologies. A noteworthy observation is the strong orientation of WB countries toward local or regional research topics, as evidenced by prominent keywords that include country names such as Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, and Kosovo.

This comparative examination suggests similarities in thematic concentrations between the EU and WB datasets, with COVID-19 and digital-related topics taking center stage in both regions.

Discussion

Given the multidisciplinary nature and broad scope of digitalization research, we reviewed the literature in the European Union and Western Balkans region to determine what research is being conducted in this area, and thus better understand the basis of the digital divide and indicate further directions of research in this field.

Our findings have answered research questions related to the main characteristics of the research carried out on digitalization between 2018 and 2023 and the structure of publications from the point of view of the year of publication, the spatial distribution of the research carried out, and the university affiliation, as well as the publication patterns occurring. Our

research shows identical growth trends between 2018 and 2022 in datasets containing publications related to digitalization issues for both regions: the European Union and Western Balkans.

This suggests a common trajectory for the development of research work in this field, indicating increasing recognition and visibility of scholarly work, and reflecting the wider involvement and impact of research from both the EU and the Western Balkan region. In this dimension, therefore, our research confirms the findings of other authors indicating the increasing importance of digitalization research, particularly in the period covering the COVID-19 pandemic and the immediate post-pandemic period (Ching-Hung *et al.*, 2021; Özdemir *et al.*, 2023; Chen & Shen, 2024). Possible reasons for this growing trend include the further establishment of the strategic position of digitalization because of external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Polyakova *et al.*, 2024) and corresponding regional policies, especially within the EU, which also influence the content and volume of academic research (Zancajo *et al.*, 2022). The perceived escalation in academic influence emphasizes the growing acknowledgment of digital transformation as a pivotal sphere of investigation in Europe. The European Union's emphasis on the economic and societal facets of digitalization is in harmony with its broader strategic aims of promoting innovation and guaranteeing comprehensive expansion (Brodny & Tutak, 2022). Western Balkan nations, contending with the obstacles of the digital gap, give precedence to the exploration of closing this disparity and harnessing digital technologies for educational intentions following the COVID-19 outbreak (Cicccone *et al.*, 2023).

The comparative analysis suggests a leading role of Spain, Italy, and Germany in the EU, and of Serbia in the Western Balkans in digitalization research, which clearly shows that these countries have the most influential position in driving research in this field in both regions. The strong position of the indicated EU countries is also confirmed by the studies of other authors (Ching-Hung *et al.*, 2021; Özdemir *et al.*, 2023; Chen & Shen, 2024). Our research has shown, however, that research at the EU scale is more evenly dispersed between countries, while in the Western Balkans it is mostly concentrated in one country (Serbia). Croatia and Slovenia, although geographically located in the Balkan region, have already become integral members of the EU, contributing to research conducted in this region (Slovenian Research Agency, 2022). The above conclusions are also

confirmed by the analysis carried out considering the affiliation of the universities.

We have also noted that publications on digitalization from both regions are most often published in the journal "Sustainability", which on the one hand may reflect a shared emphasis on sustainable development and environmental considerations in digitalization papers, but on the other hand may be an expression of a specific strategy of scientists in both regions aimed at publishing their works in journals with high impact factors, achieving a large number of citations of these publications. It is difficult to assess such a phenomenon. Some scholars stress that such journals prioritize their interests at the expense of researchers and are characterized by poor editorial practices and a lack of transparency (Moussa, 2021). However, other researchers point out that the quality of articles in these predatory journals is often unjustifiably assessed as low (Taşkın *et al.*, 2023). The extensive acceptance of "Sustainability" as a disseminating platform mirrors the significance researchers attach to accessible entry. Nevertheless, deliberations regarding quality affirmation and possible predispositions linked with accessible entry models necessitate further investigation to ensure the soundness of the research body.

Concerning the second research question, which concerned the main dimensions of digitalization explored by researchers in EU and WB countries, the answers in this regard simultaneously define the factors of the digital divide and the digitalization efforts undertaken to diminish it in these regions pointed out in the literature. Our study in this area has revealed that the exploration of digitalization within the European Union is multifaceted and involves synergies with various critical domains. We have stated that digitalization is primarily linked with the digital divide issue, and then it is considered with other aspects such as the most advanced digital technologies (artificial intelligence and blockchain), the impact of COVID-19, education, and the single digital market. An important area of research on the digital divide concerns the level of digitalization of countries, and in this context, its main measure — the DESI index — is most often considered in conjunction with such issues as digital skills, e-commerce, and economic growth. Our research has also showed that the digital divide itself is most often associated with the issues of digital literacy and digital competence, as well as the use of social media and internet accessibility. An important area of exploration is its connection with the digitalization of public services (e-government). Our findings prove that

the digital divide is studied in the EU concerning all three levels described in the literature (i.e. access, usage, and performance/capacity divide) (Lythreatis *et al.*, 2022).

In our research, however, we have observed the growing importance of research on digitalization linking it with such issues as the circular economy, digital sovereignty, internet governance, digital policy, and strategic autonomy. This is probably the result of the growing importance of issues related to sustainability (Singh *et al.*, 2022) and the broad strategic approach to digitalization applicable in the EU (Bellanova *et al.*, 2022; Brodny & Tutak, 2024). Our findings show new aspects of research on the digital divide, going beyond its previously mentioned forms, and manifesting itself in inequalities that cause problems in ensuring conditions for sustainable socio-economic development as well as digital sovereignty and security. These issues define new areas of research on the digital divide, which are currently under-researched. A full and thorough understanding of the links between the digital divide and sustainability, sovereignty, and security in the European Union is extremely important, as it has already been made clear in the literature that they are essential for the survival, resilience, and performance of the region and individual member countries in the face of the climate crisis and other ecological challenges, as well as military threats and other possible external shocks (Bellanova *et al.*, 2022; Usman *et al.*, 2024).

In turn, in the Western Balkans region, the greatest emphasis of research conducted in the field of digitalization concerns its connections with the issues of education and the COVID-19 pandemic, which determines the main dimensions of analyzing the digital divide in this region. Moreover, there is a notable focus on studying digitization in the domain of business, which reflects regional aspirations for the modernization of business processes and enhancement of economic infrastructure. The identified research areas perfectly reflect the changes taking place in socio-economic reality, as in most of the Western Balkan countries the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic led to significant digital progress in several areas, such as the digitalization of public administration, education, and healthcare systems (Ördögh, 2023). They also expose the greatest challenges in the field of digitalization in the Western Balkans, which translate into the digital divide between the countries of this region and the EU countries, such as a fragmented digital market, underdeveloped infrastructure, low levels of digital literacy and the low level of digitalization of enterprises, especially SMEs

(Zuzaku & Abazi, 2022). By better understanding the factors that affect the digital divide and the different forms that the divide can take, policymakers or managers can evaluate where further development is needed within their countries or organizations. This is even more important because the digital divide resulting from low level of digital literacy, non-compliance of the digital technologies used with European standards, low security of IT systems or lack of critical digital infrastructure may cause disruptions in specific aspects of the integration process (Stojanović & Kostić, 2018). This opens up a wide field for examining the digital divide in the context of the digital readiness of the Western Balkan countries for integration with the EU.

Conclusions

Contribution

The primary aim of this study was to analyze the main characteristics of research conducted on digitalization between 2018 and 2023, comparing the EU and Western Balkan regions. The study sought to understand the factors contributing to the digital divide and the nature of digitalization efforts in these regions, to provide insights that can inform future research and policy development aimed at enhancing digital inclusion and sustainable development. The study distinctively examines two geographical regions, the EU countries and the WB region, which includes non-EU countries. The significance of digitalization as a widely discussed and transformative subject is acknowledged, influencing various facets of society, the economy, and daily life. The crucial step of data selection is approached meticulously, with Scopus chosen as the preferred database due to its extensive coverage of diverse journals. The review process adheres to the PRISMA guidelines, incorporating specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Ultimately, a total of 1119 articles from EU countries and 277 from WB countries have been selected for comprehensive review and bibliometric analysis. Our study improves the understanding of the theoretical corpus of the digitalization research carried out in the EU and Western Balkan regions going beyond the current digital divide research framework and pointing to possible new aspects of this phenomenon. It contributes to

a better understanding of the digital divide supporting more coherent frameworks and policies to address this issue.

The analysis of publications from the years 2018–2023 indicates the growing interest of scientists in issues related to digitalization in the following years, both in the EU and the Western Balkan countries. Both data sets demonstrate the multidisciplinary nature of ongoing digitalization research, spanning fields ranging from technology and agriculture to law and education, highlighting the diverse interests of researchers across disciplines in both regions.

The analysis of the spatial distribution of publications shows that the issue of digitalization and the associated digital divide is present in research carried out in the EU countries, characterized by different levels of digitalization in the economy and society – the top ten countries with the highest publication rate include countries that are both EU leaders in the field of digitalization (the Netherlands), present a level above the EU average (Spain, France, Germany), as well as slightly below (Portugal, Belgium, Italy) and well below the EU average (Poland, Greece, Romania). The affiliation-based analysis provides valuable insights into the research output of universities, highlighting their diverse contributions and underlining the collaborative nature of the academic sector within the European Union. Both phenomena should be assessed positively. Conclusions and recommendations from research in countries with different experiences in digital transformation and having different academic backgrounds can guide measures that can narrow digital disparities and help to achieve the 2030 goals assumed for the EU's Digital Decade. At the same time, we recommend further investigation into the factors underlying the observed diffuse contribution to research outputs across various countries and universities. It will provide valuable information to policymakers, funding agencies, and researchers seeking to improve research collaboration and productivity in the domain of digitalization research, thereby resulting in more studies in this critical area to better understand and address the challenges posed by the digital divide in the European context.

In the Western Balkan countries, research on digitalization is conducted primarily by scientists from Serbia, affiliated most often with the University of Belgrade and the University of Novi Sad, who stand out as significantly more productive in publishing scientific research compared to scientists from other universities in the Western Balkan region. A noteworthy observation is the strong orientation of Western Balkan countries toward local or

regional research topics, which means that digitalization issues are considered narrowly, without reference to the wider European context. This observation should encourage governments, institutions, and scholars of Western Balkan countries to discover the reasons for the small presence of their scientists and universities among those publishing in the Scopus Database and take actions to foster a robust research environment and to enhance research collaboration and networks across the Western Balkan region and with EU countries to increase scholarly contributions.

Our research underscores the different research priorities in the EU and WB regions, with both regions exploring the multifaceted dimensions of the digital landscape while allocating emphasis across specific themes. There is a visible focus in research done by EU scientists on the intersection of digital technologies, economic advancements, and sustainable development. The exploration of digitalization within the European Union links it with various critical domains, covered by the EU's digital strategy. Greater attention to the circular economy, digital sovereignty, internet governance, digital policy, strategic autonomy, and panel data suggests alignment with changing priorities and challenges in the EU, which shows new emerging dimensions in which the digital divide should be studied. Research focusing directly on the digital divide places particular emphasis on aspects such as digital literacy, digital competence, education, social media, internet accessibility, and e-government, which indicates that all types of the digital divide are studied, but with a particular focus on the usage divide associated with digital literacy.

In turn, digitalization research in the Western Balkans region focuses on the term "COVID-19" and significantly explores topics related to education and learning skills and innovations. They also explore digitalization in a business context, covering concepts such as sustainability, entrepreneurship, industry 4.0, and digital platforms, as well as examining digital technologies in the areas of e-learning and the Internet. The focus on COVID-19 reflects researchers' response to the global crisis, and the gradual shift towards topics related to online learning and media means constantly adapting to changing circumstances and changing research needs. Research directions including digital marketing, e-learning, higher education, and company performance signal the recognition of the growing importance of digital technologies in shaping various aspects of the business landscape regulated by national strategies, including Smart Specialization Strategy (S3). However, there is some research gap emerging, related to poor recog-

dition of the digital readiness of the Western Balkan countries for their integration with the EU and the multi-faceted assessment of the scale and nature of the existing digital divide.

Future research could also conduct longitudinal studies to track the progress and impact of digitalization efforts in both EU and Western Balkan countries and their effectiveness in addressing the digital divide over a more extended period. This would provide deeper insights into the long-term effects of digital policies and interventions. Analyzing and comparing digital policies between EU countries and Western Balkan countries can uncover best practices and successful strategies that can be adopted across regions to bridge the digital divide.

Investigating the role of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things in digital transformation efforts across different socio-economic contexts could provide valuable insights into their potential to accelerate digital inclusion and address the digital divide. Future studies could explore the direct and indirect impacts of digitalization on economic development, employment, and productivity in both regions, helping to quantify the benefits of digital investments. Research on cross-regional collaborations and partnerships in digital initiatives between the EU and Western Balkan countries can highlight the benefits and challenges of such collaborations and offer recommendations for enhancing cooperative efforts. Their focus should be also on how partnerships between the EU and Western Balkan countries can enhance digital inclusion and foster sustainable digital development.

In-depth case studies of specific digitalization projects or initiatives counteracting the digital divide within individual countries or regions can provide practical examples of success stories and lessons learned, offering valuable guidance for policymakers and practitioners. Evaluating the effectiveness of digital literacy programs and initiatives aimed at different demographic groups can provide insights into how best to tailor these programs to meet the needs of various populations, particularly in under-served areas.

Our findings prompt us to formulate certain recommendations resulting from the analyzed body of literature. To better and more effectively bridge the digital gap we recommend policymakers in the EU and Western Balkans countries to:

- Enhance Digital Literacy Programs: implement and support digital literacy initiatives targeting marginalized groups, including the elderly, low-income individuals, and rural populations, to ensure inclusive participation in the digital economy, implement policies that integrate digital tools and resources in educational systems, ensuring equitable access to digital learning opportunities for all pupils and students.
- Strengthen Digital Infrastructure: invest in robust digital infrastructure to bridge the connectivity gap, particularly in underdeveloped and rural areas, ensuring all citizens have access to high-speed internet and digital services.
- Support Emerging Technologies: promote the adoption and integration of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things in the public and private sectors to accelerate digital transformation.
- Develop Comprehensive Digital Policies: formulate and implement comprehensive digital strategies that address the multifaceted aspects of digitalization, including economic development, social inclusion, and sustainability.
- Facilitate Cross-Regional Collaborations: encourage and support cross-regional collaborations between the EU and Western Balkan countries to share best practices, resources, and knowledge in digitalization efforts, with particular focus on those that counteract the digital divide.
- Focus on Digital Sovereignty and Security: prioritize digital sovereignty and cybersecurity in policy frameworks to ensure the resilience and security of digital infrastructures against external threats and protect vulnerable groups.
- Promote Research and Development: support R&D initiatives in digital technologies and applications to foster innovation and maintain a competitive edge in the global digital landscape.
- Encourage Public-Private Partnerships: foster partnerships between government, private sector, and academia to leverage resources, expertise, and innovations for comprehensive digital transformation.
- Monitor and Evaluate Policy Impact: establish mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the impact of digital policies and initiatives to ensure they effectively address the digital divide and promote continuous improvement.

The conclusions drawn from our research for the EU and Western Balkans regions and the recommendations we have formulated may contribute to shaping more coherent and effective frameworks and policies within the EU and Western Balkans regions to address challenges related to digitalization and the digital divide. They address the issues which have been deeply recognized in the literature, but also those that are just emerging.

The analysis of publications on digitalization in the EU and Western Balkan countries shows a growing research landscape. The focus on the digital divide, policy implications, and technological advancements reflects the multifaceted nature of digitalization. EU countries have more publications, but Western Balkan countries are improving. This study adds to the discourse on digitalization and provides a foundation for future research and policy considerations. The study has limitations, including potential bias in the chosen databases and search criteria, which should be acknowledged for a comprehensive interpretation of the findings.

Limitations

This study provides bibliometric insights into a diverse range of research articles within the EU and WB regions, encompassing both broad research topics and those specifically focused on the digital domain. The data were sourced from the Scopus database. While the study aims for objectivity and comprehensiveness, it is not without limitations. Firstly, non-English articles, though valuable, may not be present in the Scopus database, potentially limiting the scope of the analysis. Bibliometric data are subject to change over time, and conclusions drawn in this study may evolve accordingly. Regular updates are recommended to maintain relevance. The nature of bibliometric analysis may not capture real-time situations, particularly regarding recently published articles that may not have accumulated substantial citations yet. Consequently, the analysis might not fully represent the unfolding trends and impact of such articles over time.

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Annex

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram applied on EU and WB datasets

Figure 2. Number of articles by year in a) EU and b) Western Balkan Countries

Figure 3. Number of articles per country in a) EU and b) Western Balkan

Figure 4. Number of articles by universities in EU Countries

Figure 5. Number of articles by universities in Western Balkan Countries

Figure 6. Top 10 Most Popular Journals in a) EU and b) Western Balkan Datasets

Figure 7. Keywords used in the EU dataset (%)

Figure 8. Keywords used in the WB dataset (%)

Figure 9. Keywords related to the digit in the EU dataset (%)

Figure 10. Keywords related to the digit in the WB dataset (%)

Figure 13. Network map of the trend topics according to the keywords in the EU dataset

Figure 14. Network map of the trend topics according to the keywords in the WB dataset

